

Processes Driving Exchange at Cape Hatteras (PEACH) PIESs and AP Technical Report – Part 1

*Pressure Sensor Equipped Inverted Echo Sounders (PIESs) and Articulating Profiler (AP)
Descriptions of the L0 to L3 PIES data*

Collaborative Research: An Observational and Modeling Study of the Physical Processes
Driving Exchanges between the Shelf and the Deep Ocean At Cape Hatteras
(or Processes Driving Exchange at Cape Hatteras, PEACH)

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Notes:

18 Sept., 2020: An earlier draft of this report from 23 Nov. 2018 had truncated PIES pressure, temperature and acoustic travel time files (missing the first month of data); this revised report contains the full records.

02 Oct., 2020: A separate **PEACH PIESs and AP Technical Report - Part 2** will include discussion of L4 PIES data products and will report on auxiliary data including the AP, hydrographic profiles (including those used in building a GEM from Spray gliders and Argo floats), and shipboard data.

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1. PEACH Program

The PEACH project aims to identify the processes that control the exchange of waters between the shelves along the eastern seaboard of the U.S. (the Middle Atlantic Bight and Southern Atlantic Bight) and the open ocean. The PEACH project includes remote sensing and in situ observations—comprising radars, moored platforms and gliders (**Figure 1**)—as well as a numerical modeling component.

Figure 1. PEACH array off of Cape Hatteras showing moored instruments, glider tracks, radar coverage and other regional observations (as in Figure 1 of the AR-15 Cruise Report, with the addition of the AP mooring deployed on AR-33).

1.1 PEACH PIES and Articulating Profiler Mooring

The PEACH PIES array comprised 5 Current-and-Pressure sensor equipped Inverted Echo Sounders (CPIESs) and 2 Doppler current profiler equipped inverted echo sounders (DCPS-PIESs) which were deployed in April 2017. An additional asset – a tall mooring with an Articulating Profiler, an upward-looking ADCP and 2 Microcats (AP) – was added to the array in January 2018.

The primary goal of the PEACH PIES part of the in situ array is to characterize the Gulf Stream (position, strength, orientation, meander characteristics) approaching and downstream of this western boundary current's separation point near Cape Hatteras. These observations are being used to investigate the Gulf Stream's influence on the region's shelf/open ocean exchange processes. The AP mooring provides additional information (1) about the upper ocean (from the upward-looking ADCP) between the MAB and the separated Gulf Stream and (2) about the equatorward-flowing Deep Western Boundary Current (DWBC) on its approach to Cape Hatteras. The DWBC may interact with the Gulf Stream and thereby indirectly influence shelf/open ocean exchange processes here.

2. Cruise Notes

The PEACH Array was deployed on cruise AR-15 (15-29 April 2017), was serviced on cruise AR-26 (8-21 January 2018) and was recovered on cruise AR-33 (17-29 November 2018), all from the from the *R/V Neil Armstrong* sailing from Woods Hole to Woods Hole (see **Table 1** for launch and recovery dates). 7 PIESs (comprising 5 CPIESs and 2 DCPS-PIESs) were deployed in April 2017. The 5 PIESs were successfully recovered in November 2018. The 2 DCPS-PIESs were not recovered. On each of the three PEACH cruises, full-water column CTD casts were collected at each of the 7 PIESs sites. Three Argo floats were deployed at or near the PIES sites on AR-33. Details of the PEACH PIESs deployments can be found in the AR-15 Cruise Report and Appendix¹. Details of the PEACH PIESs recoveries are below, with additional information about the turn-around and recovery cruises in an AR-26 Cruise Report (presently in preparation) and AR-33 Cruise Report².

The AP mooring was deployed in January 2018 and was recovered in November 2018. There was a CTD cast at deployment, but not at recovery because this site is so close to PI and there were time constraints due to the weather. Details of the AP Mooring recovery are below and in a part 2 to this technical report.

2.1 AR-33 Narrative

Due to poor weather the cruise left Woods Hole on Saturday 17 November 2018, a day later than scheduled. We transited directly to site A1 and from there headed southeast along the **line GS1** conducting an ADCP/XBT section towards P4, the most offshore PEACH site on the Sargasso Sea side of the Gulf Stream. (See the AR-33 Cruise report for cruise track and sections details).

For PIESs recovery operations, we used the *R/V Neil Armstrong*'s through-hull transducer and the PIES-code-enabled 8011M Edgetech deck unit (SN 48240) with TRAX running on a Toughbook computer. Deckbox settings that worked most reliably for the PIES communications were: **Transmit Level = 3**; **Receive Level = 6**. The ship's Radio Direction Finder (RDF) detected all of the PIESs that surfaced (set to 156.875 MHz). The ship's 38 kHz ADCP was used to calculate the expected drift of each CPIESs during its ascent to the sea surface (CPIES rise rate = 94 m/min; the DCPS-PIES rise rate is still uncertain, though URI has suggested possibly 65 to 75 m/min).

To determine the CPIESs' surfacing-locations on AR-33, the PEACH PIES target locations from the AR-15 Cruise Report, Table 4 (where these were calculated from the instrument's drop location, Table 2, and the observed 38 kHz ADCP velocities at the time of deployment) were used as the CPIESs' starting locations. Then the velocity profiles observed on AR-33 with the 38kHz ADCP were used to calculate the CPIES's expected surfacing location. This procedure worked very well.

¹ Available at:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/11cNEcpwEihtxeRqhHBSM5XhRhZZhHKyK/view?usp=sharing> and <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ToRSQXPTm2YgMmsFCLlBT6EKGYF1kISD/view?usp=sharing>

² Available at:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1 fhIwnCXUDJ5gI36pT1lmkaIdIC3n026/view?usp=sharing>.

Monday 19 November 2018 (late Sunday 18 November, local time). We arrived at site **P4** and tried to communicate with WHOI's DCPS-PIES **SN 361**. We heard no sample pings and no responses to ACS commands. In the meantime, we did the last of the XBT launches for GS1 (X12, T7_20181119044622.edf) and conducted a full-water column CTD cast (001, ar31c001.hex) with 2 sets of 4 each bottles for Argo Program sensor tests (S. Wijffels). During the CTD upcast we still heard nothing from the DCPS-PIES. The second Edgetech we had on board was not CPIES-code-enabled, so we tried using the Benthos UDB-9000 with its over-the-side transducer. It also did not hear the DCPS-PIES. We decided to try a blind recovery since the release batteries are completely separate from the system batteries. We calculated the expected drift, which was 280 m towards 30°T (note that there seemed to be an eddy here at recovery; during the deployment, the currents were so weak that there was no expected drift). We gave 5 release commands in succession directly over the instrument with ship noise turned off, noting the time of the first and last. We calculated the range of expected rise times (using 15-20 minute burn time and 65 to 75 m/min rise times), moved offsite slightly and waited for the surfacing time plus about an extra hour. We saw nothing at the surface and heard nothing on the RDF. The only possible chance of anything was that several people may have seen a subsurface light off the starboard bow – maybe one or two sets of flashes? Conditions were calm and sea state was relatively flat. After the failed recovery, we deployed the 1st Argo float **SN 7514** and steamed towards P3. Half way between P4 and P3 we deployed the 2nd Argo float, **SN 11030**.

We arrived at site **P3** (URI's DCPS-PIES, **SN 355**). To verify that the communications were OK on the ship-side, we used the Edgetech deckbox/throughhull transducer as an echosounder (set send and receive frequencies to 12 kHz and transponded off the bottom). We conducted a full-water column CTD cast (002, ar31c002.hex). During this cast the altimeter alarmed when the CTD entered the water but turned off at about 70 m depth. After the CTD cast we deployed the third Argo float (**SN 15092**). Then we had the ship move to the PIES deployment location (not the Target location that we had calculated from the 400 m drift at deployment, but the deployment location where the instrument was dropped). We had the ship shut off all 12 kHz noise (bow thruster, Knudsen and just in case all the ADCPs) and tried communications first with the Edgetech/through hull and then with the UDB9000 over the side. We did the echosounder range test and successfully saw the bottom at 2753 m. We then failed communications with DCPS-PIES (we did not hear samples nor replies to ACS commands). We did not send a release command.

Note: we returned to this site on 25 November to send a release command as a last ditch effort for recovery. We used the following procedure for recovery and feel it is likely that the instrument did not surface:

1. We arrived at the P3 site (this is the site where we deployed the instrument + a 400 m drift which we had calculated from the currents at deployment) and reconfirmed that the PIES was not responding to ACS commands and was not sampling.
2. We ran the 38 kHz ADCP for a bit and then calculated the expected drift during PIES ascent. I did this for two rise rates: 65 m/min and 75 m/min. The results were between 550 and 650 m, so we set 600 m downstream of the P3 site as the expected surfacing site.
3. Without moving the ship, we had the ship turn off all potential 12 kHz noise (Knudsen, bow thruster) and sent the release command 5 times...mostly at the same settings we used at the other sites and one last time with the transmit amplitude increased. We noted the times of first and last release command sent.

4. With the range of release command times, rise rates and burn times from 12-25 minutes we calculated the range of expected surfacing times of 49 to 67 minutes.
5. We manned the bridge, had the RDF on and waited. There was no sign of the PIES (unfortunately it was not evening time, so the strobe wouldn't really have shown up, but the conditions were quite good...clear, relatively small waves).
6. Once a significant amount of time passed (more than the longest expected surfacing time), we thought the PIES might be rising slower than expected (maybe due to a swamped float?) and thought that the PIES might be in the upper ocean high velocity layer longer than we had anticipated. So we moved the ship back to the deployment location and slowly moved the ship in the direction of the current to try to catch up to the PIES in case it had been swept further than we thought. We proceeded in this direction for before calling off the search because we ran out of time.

We found no evidence that the instrument surfaced.

A3 and B1 (except chain and anchor) were successfully recovered.

Tuesday November 20 (late Monday Nov 19, local), we arrived at CPIES site **P2 (SN 107)**. Heard sampling, CPIES responded to ACS commands. We conducted a full-water column CTD cast (005, ar31c005.hex) to within 2 m of the bottom. We calculated a drift (340 m) and total surfacing time. The CPIES surfaced in the expected time. The 10-m float recovery line was wrapped around the yellow hard hat, which made getting it on to the ship a little challenging. The Bosun (Pete) directly grabbed the bridle on the white hardhat.

We arrived at CPIES site **P1 (SN 102)** and heard the CPIES sample and reply to ACS commands. A full water column CTD cast was conducted here (006, ar31c006.hex). There were very weak currents so the expected drift was essentially 0. Recovery went without a hitch. When downloading the data from this instrument we did note some corrosion around the communication cable (maybe at the ground pin).

We arrived at the **AP** site around 8:15 AM (local) and had the profiler on board by about 9:30 AM (local). Since this site is close to P1 we did not conduct another CTD cast.

Next we transited to A1, but could not talk to the instrument (later it turned out that it had drifted during deployment and we found it and successfully recovered it). We also recovered a glider (Angus). We went to site A2, but initially to the wrong site. When we did finally arrive at the correct site, we could talk to it, but it was too late to release (we needed daylight to recover this instrument).

On Wednesday November 21 (evening November 20, local) we arrived at CPIES site **P5 (SN 112)**. We did a full-water column CTD cast (009, ar31c009.hex). This is the northernmost of the southern CPIES sites (closest to the point). During the cast, we think we reached to the top of the Upper Labrador Sea Water at about 600 m depth (based on T, S and high oxygen). The 38 kHz ADCP also shows that there was also a strong shear at this depth between northeastward flowing Gulf Stream and southwestward flowing DWBC. We estimated the drift from the 38 kHz (305 m) and recovered successfully.

On our transit from P5 southwestward towards P6 we observed the deep counterflow continuously with the 38 kHz ADCP while underway. We arrived at CPIES site **P6 (SN 114)** and heard the instrument sampling while positioning the ship. We did a full-water depth CTD cast (010, ar31c010.hex). After the cast with the ship well positioned for the wind and currents and a drift of 400 m, we could not communicate with the CPIES because of the prop wash over the transducer. We repositioned, sent the release command and then repositioned again and recovered successfully.

We tried to recover A5 (including dragging) but were unsuccessful. We recovered B2.

On Wednesday November 22 we arrived at CPIES site **P7 (SN 166)**. We did a CTD cast at this site (013, ar31c013.hex). This cast included 10 minute soaks at two depths as part of the Argo sensor testing. We calculated an expected drift here (218 m towards 209°T) which was opposite the surface currents due to the relatively strong flows in the DWBC layer. In contrast to all of the other TRAX traces during recovery, this one did not have an echo trace off the bottom, only the trace of the instrument. Perhaps this is due to the strong slope or due to the bottom material. The instrument was recovered successfully.

3. CPIES Data

3.1 CPIES sensors and instrument settings

CPIESs provide measures of bottom pressure, bottom temperature, round-trip surface-to-bottom acoustic travel time and horizontal velocities and temperature 50 m above the seabed. The CPIESs' PAROS pressure sensors were each model 46k. The CPIESs' current sensors were Aanderaa Zpulse 4930R except for the sensor on SN 102 (site P1) which was a DCS 3820R. See Table 5 'CPIES/DCPS vitals' in the AR-15 Cruise Report for the other specs for the CPIES sensor components.

Each of the 5 CPIESs was set to the following sampling schedule (see also the .txt files in the L0/mission_setups):

- Travel Time Measurements: 4 pings every 10 minutes
- Pressure and Temperature measured every 10 minutes
- DCS measurement every 30 minutes

3.2 CPIES data levels

Level 0 (L0) – *raw data from the platform, often in format from manufacturer. Retained as the most fundamental form of the observations but often not used in analysis.* For CPIESs, these are the .dat files saved as raw output by the instrument. See the Inverted Echo Sounder User's Manual IES Model 6.2C (Section 4 DATA RECOVERY and ANALYSIS – 4.2.1 File Types) for further details of the data formats. Also included are the .txt files automatically saved at instrument deployment by the computer used for mission set up.

Level 1 (L1) – *initially-processed data, retaining the original sampling scheme (in time-space).* For CPIESs, these are the data from the instruments converted from .dat format to .mat format (using IES_GUIDAT2MAT), and include the raw ping data (24 per hour) for round trip acoustic travel time. See the Appendix (section A.1) for plots.

Level 2 (L2) – similar to L1 but with further QC, and processing, and some calibrations applied. For CPIPEs, there are three components of L2 data: (1) hourly data records, (2) low pass filtered data records, and (3) the amplitude and phase of the barotropic tides. The processing is done with the URI codes using IES_GUIDRIVER. This step includes despiking acoustic travel time and temperature records, and identifying and removing any pressure-sensor drifts prior to tidal analysis of pressures. Currents are relative to magnetic north not True North (and require correction, applied in L3, to account for local magnetic declination). See the Appendix (section A.2) for plots and the Inverted Echo Sounder Data Processing Manual (Kennelly et al., 2007) for a description of the processing tools and file naming convention.

Level 3 (L3) – often gridding of data in time or space. For the CPIPEs, the L3 velocity records are corrected to True North, otherwise the L3 time series records are as in L2. In addition to renaming the uncorrected velocity records and appending the corrected velocity records, the L3 files are also appended to include each CPIPE site’s (1) magnetic declination, (2) latitude, (3) longitude and (4) depth. Codes to do this L3 processing were run in two steps: Step_1_Add_lat_lon_depths.m and Step_2_Correct_PEACH_PIES_currents.m.³

Level 4 (L4) – L4 processed CPIPE data, and derived products and indexes are being generated and will be reported on in Part 2 of this Technical Report. This will include the formation Gravest Empirical Mode (GEM) lookup table(s) to interpret acoustic travel time records. From these lookup tables and the L2/L3 CPIPE records we may generate time series at each site of: (1) density profiles, (2) temperature profiles and (3) salinity profiles as well as (4) SSH (steric plus non-steric), (5) thermocline depth, and (6) any basin-mode pressure signals. In addition, we may identify time series of (7) internal tides. Derived indexes will include (8) Gulf Stream position and (9) orientation.

3.3 CPIPE data processing procedure

The L0 raw (.dat) files collected by the CPIPEs were converted to L1 .mat files using IES_GUIDAT2MAT (run on Andres’ mac). The figures saved during this .dat to .mat processing step are in the Appendix of this report.

Table 1. CPIPEs and AP launch and recovery info (collected from deployment and recovery logs).

Site/SN	Launch Time (GMT)	Recover Time (GMT)	Clock Drift (s)
P1 102	2017 April 17 13:50	2018 November 20 11:32	-37
P2 107	2017 April 17 18:08	2018 November 20 06:58	-53
P5 112	2017 April 22 19:56	2018 November 21 04:15	-57
P6 114	2017 April 22 15:19	2018 November 21 11:22	-46
P7 166	2017 April 21 18:58	2018 November 22 10:07	-25
AP	2018 January 16 15:35	2018 November 20 14:30	NA

The next step in processing is running the IES_GUIDRIVER on the .mat files. This was run on the Toughbook (because RESPO doesn’t work on the mac) and copied back onto the mac. Note: these files were originally processed with IES_GUIDRIVER in November 2018 but the first month of data were accidentally truncated; we reran the processing in September 2020 and included the full PIES data records. (The first processing also used a 3-day low pass filter cutoff; this reprocessed data used a 2-day low pass filter instead to avoid interfering with the Gulf Stream frontal meander scale, while still filtering the (internal + barotropic) tidal signal from the acoustic travel time record.) Processing settings (4th order, 2-day low pass Butterworth filter)

³/Users/Sverdrup/Documents/Cruises/PEACH_2018_recovery/Technical_report/L3_processing.

were as shown in the screen grab below (**Figure 2**) and using the parameters in **Table 1** with each instrument’s launch time, recovery time and clock drift as noted on recovery.

Figure 2. Screen grab showing the settings (in this case for P6) used to process the CPIESs with IES_GUIDRIVER.

3.4 CPIES L2 and L3 processed data

Plots of the L1 and L2 data for each CPIES are included in the Appendix. The plots in this section show various aspects of the L3 processed (or L2 as indicated) data and preliminary analysis of these processed data.

Table 2. Sites and waters depths appended to L3 CPIES data³

Instrument Site	Latitude ¹ (°N)	Longitude ¹ (°W)	Water Depth ² (m)
P1	35.8517	74.6167	1776
P2	35.6894	74.3500	2349
P5	35.3080	74.8202	1798
P6	34.9400	75.1664	1275
P7	34.5000	75.6000	1313
AP	35.7512	74.6097	1516

¹ Collected from subset of IES_target_locs.mat and from AR33 AP recovery log sheet.

² For the CPIESs, depths are calculated from the time-averaged pressure record minus mean atmospheric pressure (**10.13 dbar**) and converted to meters. For the AP, the water depth is calculated by interpolation of bathymetry data.

³ Processing and appending information to L3 was done with cd/Users/Sverdrup/Documents/Cruises/PEACH_2018_recovery/Technical_report/L3_processing/Add_lat_lon_depths.m.

Figure 3. Map of PEACH CPIES (circles) and AP (triangle) locations.

3.4.1 Acoustic travel time records

Figure 4. Processed (L2 and L3) acoustic travel time records. Left panels: time series of hourly (blue) and 2-day low pass filtered (red) records. In each panel, the y-axis shows a 20 ms range and green lines denote: 2017 9 19 Jose; 2017 9 27 Maria; 2018 7 8 Chris; 2018 9 14 Florence from `get_event_timing.m`. Right panels: τ_{LP} spectra with 136-day windows and 50% overlap. Lines denote periods at: 100-day (black), 50-day (magenta), 20-day (orange), 10-day (grey) and 5-day period (red).

Figure 5. Spectra of the processed hourly acoustic travel time records. In addition to the tidal periods indicated (black lines, from low to high frequency these are diurnal: Q1, O1, P1, K1 and semidiurnal: N2, M2, S2, K2), periods are highlighted at 50-day (magenta), 20-day (orange), 11.1-day (grey), 5.002-day (red), 3.703-day (yellow), and 3.03-day (green) periods. Window is 2400 hours (100 days) with 50% overlap.

3.4.2 Pressure records

3.4.2.1 Drifts and tides

Figure 6. Pressure drifts. Hourly pressure records with the barotropic tides removed (blue) and the component of this that is due to pressure sensor drift (red).

Table 3. Amplitudes and phases of the barotropic tide at each CPIES site as determined by the Response Method and the pressure records.

Site ID	Tide Amplitude (dbar) and Phase (°)															
	O1		K1		Q1		P1		M2		K2		N2		S2	
P1	0.071	190.89	0.091	186.87	0.015	187.53	0.030	187.71	0.426	1.26	0.018	30.34	0.102	340.66	0.080	29.34
P2	0.070	192.99	0.091	188.99	0.015	189.90	0.030	189.79	0.424	5.20	0.018	34.73	0.101	344.49	0.080	33.62
P5	0.072	194.78	0.091	191.84	0.017	189.07	0.030	192.92	0.418	7.25	0.018	37.42	0.099	347.63	0.077	35.77
P6	0.070	193.19	0.091	188.81	0.015	190.92	0.030	189.54	0.419	3.45	0.017	31.36	0.100	342.56	0.077	30.67
P7	0.071	191.09	0.092	186.95	0.016	187.68	0.030	187.79	0.422	358.55	0.017	26.49	0.101	338.04	0.077	25.73

Figure 7. Processed (L2 and L3) pressure records (dedrifted, and detided). Left panels: dedrifted, detided, hourly (blue) and 2-day lowpass filtered (red) pressure records. In each panel, the green lines denote: 2017 9 19 Jose; 2017 9 27 Maria; 2018 7 8 Chris; 2018 9 14 Florence from get_event_timing.m. Right panels: P_{LP} spectra with 136-day windows and 50% overlap

3.4.3 Temperature records (from PAROS sensor)

Figure 8. Processed (L2 and L3) temperatures ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). Left panels: hourly (blue) and 2-day lowpass filtered (red) temperature records from the CPIES Paros sensors. In each panel, the green lines denote: 2017 9 19 Jose; 2017 9 27 Maria; 2018 7 8 Chris; 2018 9 14 Florence from `get_event_timing.m`. Right panels: T_{LP} spectra with 136-day windows and 50% overlap.

3.4.4 L2 and L3 Current meter records

Figure 9. Processed (L2) current meter records hourly (blue) and 2-day lowpass filtered (red) at P1 showing u and v velocity components and stick plots (with no magnetic correction applied yet) as well as speed (cm/s) and temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) as measured by the current meter heads, all 50 m above the bottom. Green lines denote: 2017 9 19 Jose; 2017 9 27 Maria; 2018 7 8 Chris; 2018 9 14 Florence from get_event_timing.m.

Figure 10. Processed (L2) current meter records hourly (blue) and 2-day lowpass filtered (red) at P2 showing u and v velocity components and stick plots (with no magnetic correction applied yet) as well as speed (cm/s) and temperature (C) as measured by the current meter heads, all 50 m above the bottom. Green lines denote: 2017 9 19 Jose; 2017 9 27 Maria; 2018 7 8 Chris; 2018 9 14 Florence from `get_event_timing.m`

Figure 11. Processed (L2) current meter records hourly (blue) and 2-day lowpass filtered (red) at P5 showing u and v velocity components and stick plots (with no magnetic correction applied yet) as well as speed (cm/s) and temperature (C) as measured by the current meter heads, all 50 m above the bottom. Green lines denote: 2017 9 19 Jose; 2017 9 27 Maria; 2018 7 8 Chris; 2018 9 14 Florence from `get_event_timing.m`.

Figure 12. Processed (L2) current meter records hourly (blue) and 2-day lowpass filtered (red) at P6 showing u and v velocity components and stick plots (with no magnetic correction applied yet) as well as speed (cm/s) and temperature (C) as measured by the current meter heads, all 50 m above the bottom. Green lines denote: 2017 9 19 Jose; 2017 9 27 Maria; 2018 7 8 Chris; 2018 9 14 Florence from `get_event_timing.m`.

Figure 13. Processed (L2) current meter records hourly (blue) and 2-day lowpass filtered (red) at P7 showing u and v velocity components and stick plots (with no magnetic correction applied yet) as well as speed (cm/s) and temperature (C) as measured by the current meter heads, all 50 m above the bottom. Green lines denote: 2017 9 19 Jose; 2017 9 27 Maria; 2018 7 8 Chris; 2018 9 14 Florence from get_event_timing.m.

3.4.4.1 Corrections for magnetic declination (to get from L2 to L3 current records)

These CRIESs' L2 velocity records referenced to local magnetic north are corrected for the local magnetic declinations (**Table 4**) to rotate to True North to produce L3 data records. The original, uncorrected L2 time series (P#.u, P#.v, P#lp.u, P#lp.v) are renamed and retained in the L3 files as (P#.u_uncorrected, P#.v_uncorrected, P#lp.u_uncorrected, P#lp.v_uncorrected).

Magnetic declinations are assumed to be spatially varying across the array (**Table 4**), but fixed in time using the mid-point of time series (1/20/2018 for PIES; 1/6/2018 for AP to be consistent with Dan T.'s processing of the upward looking ADCP). The L3 records are appended to include each site's magnetic declination (mag_decl). Using each instrument's latitude and longitudes, the following website is used: <https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/geomag/calculators/magcalc.shtml> with model IGRF2015.

Table 4. Magnetic declinations used to correct u and v measured by the CRIESs' current sensors and by the AP.¹

Site #	Site name	Lon. (°W)	Lat. (°N)	IGRF2015 magnetic decl. (°W)	Notes:
13	P1	74.6170	35.8514	11.59	using depl. mid-date of 1/20/2018
14	P2	74.3506	35.6890	11.69	using depl. mid-date of 1/20/2018
15	P3	74.1726	35.5579	11.76	not recovered
16	P4	73.7896	35.2801	11.9	not recovered
17	P5	74.8212	35.3063	11.38	using depl. mid-date of 1/20/2018
18	P6	75.1691	34.9372	11.13	using depl. mid-date of 1/20/2018
19	P7	75.6013	34.4986	10.82	using depl. mid-date of 1/20/2018
20	AP	74.6097	35.7512	11.58	uses depl. mid-date of 6/20/2018

¹ Table generated from data in Table_4_current_meters_declination.xlsx; these values are hard coded into cd/Users/Sverdrup/Documents/Cruises/PEACH_2018_recovery/Technical_report/L3_processing/Correct_PEACH_PIES_currents.m which appended the values onto the L3 records.

The time-mean values (L3, corrected to True North, shown in **Figure 14**) are appended to the L3 hourly P#.mat and 2-day low-pass filtered P#lp.mat files as:

P#.u_mean

P#.v_mean

P#lp.u_mean

P#lp.v_mean

showing the eastward (u) and northward (v) velocities.

The time-varying values (L3, corrected to True North, shown for each site together with variance ellipses, **Figure 15**) are appended to the L3 hourly P#.mat and 2-day low-pass filtered P#lp.mat files as:

P#.u

P#.v

P#lp.u

P#lp.v

showing the eastward (u) and northward (v) velocities.

3.4.4.2 Mean L3 currents

Figure 14 Time-averaged, corrected (rotated to true north) L3 near-bottom currents (50 m above the bottom) at the CPIES sites. Blue dots are PEACH assets; red circles denote recovered CPIESs. Isobaths shown at 50, 100, 500 (heavy), 1000, 1500, 2000, 2500 and 3000 m depths with bathymetry from `caphat_coast.mat` and processing to get L3 currents run with `/Users/Sverdrup/Documents/Cruises/PEACH_2018_recovery/Technical_report/L3_processing/Correct_PEACH_PIES_currents.m`.

3.4.4.3 Time-varying L3 currents

Figure 15. 95% confidence interval error ellipses for the L3 hourly (left) and 2-day low pass filtered (right) currents (all corrected to true north) with the means (yellow stars) indicated. Made with `/Users/Sverdrup/Documents/Cruises/PEACH_2018_recovery/Technical_report/figures/Figure_15_hourly_current_variance_ellipses.m` and `Figure_15_lp_current_variance_ellipses.m`.

Further analysis is needed, but a preliminary examination of P6, where the mean flow is across the isobaths (see [Figure 14](#)), suggests that there are two different processes at play here (i.e., a pdf of the velocities seems to be bimodal, Figure 16). The cause of the strong southeastward "events" is under investigation, as is the reason for the mean cross-isobath flow.

Figure 16. Histograms of L3 hourly eastward, u and northward, v (corrected for magnetic declination) velocity components at site P6, where the mean flow is cross isobath. /Users/Sverdrup/Documents/Cruises/PEACH_2018_recovery/Technical_report/figuresFigure_16_hourly_current_histogram.m

Reference

Kennelly, M. A., K. L. Tracey and D. R. Watts, 2007, Inverted Echo Sounder Data Processing Manual, GSO Technical Report, 2007-02.